

QUINOLINE DERIVATIVES. PART IX

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For pharmacological study against amoebiasis, some quinoline derivatives, in which both 8-ethoxyquinoline residue and the fundamental nucleus of Carbarsone or Stovarsol are present, have been prepared.

As a result of extensive clinical trials of various chemotherapeutic drugs on cases of amoebic dysentery in the army, Leishman and Kelsall (*Lancet*, 1944, p. 231) have found that there are some relapsing cases which resist the action of all these drugs. They have felt the urgent need for the discovery of a new amoebicidal drug, which will effect cure in chronic and relapsing cases.

Derivatives of 8-hydroxyquinoline, such as Chinosol, Yatren and Vioform, are widely used in cases of amoebic dysentery. Again organo-arsenical compounds, such as Carbarsone and Stovarsol (3-acetylamino-4-hydroxyphenylarsonic acid), are also used as useful amoebicidal drugs. It was thought of interest to prepare compounds in which both 8-hydroxyquinoline or its derivative and the fundamental nucleus of Carbarsone or Stovarsol are present, and to find out if such compounds possess amoebicidal properties.

As on direct sulphonation, and so with chlorosulphonic acid, 8-hydroxyquinoline yields 8-hydroxyquinoline-5-sulphonic acid, the iodo derivative of which constitutes the drug, Yatren. However, 8-ethoxyquinoline yields, with chlorosulphonic acid, 8-ethoxyquinoline-5-sulphonyl chloride which has been condensed with *p*-arsaniic acid and with 3-amino-4-hydroxyphenylarsonic acid to give respectively the compounds (I) and (II), the pharmacological examination of which is under investigation.

[(I), R = -NH-C₆H₄-AsO(OH)₂ (1 : 4). (II), R = -NH-C₆H₃(OH)-AsO(OH)₂ (3 : 4 : 1)]

EXPERIMENTAL

8-Ethoxyquinoline was prepared according to the method of Fischer and Renouf (*Ber.*, 1884, 17, 759), b.p. 285-86°, straw-coloured, heavy liquid, yield 55 g. from 60 g. of 8-hydroxyquinoline.

8-Ethoxyquinoline-5-sulphonyl Chloride.—In a round-bottomed flask, fitted with a mechanical stirrer, were placed 75 g. of chlorosulphonic acid, previously distilled from a glass retort. The flask was cooled to about 12°. To the chlorosulphonic acid was added gradually 17 g. of 8-ethoxyquinoline, temperature being maintained between 12° and 15°. After the addition was over, the mixture was heated at 65°-70° in an oil-bath for about 3 hours. The syrupy liquid was cooled in ice and poured slowly, with stirring, into excess of melting ice. A brown, clear solution was obtained which was immediately saturated with sodium chloride. The clear thick solution, on scratching and standing for about

30 minutes, deposited a voluminous precipitate, which was filtered, pressed on the Buchner and dried quickly on a porous plate, yield 16 g. The crude sulphonyl chloride was used for subsequent operations without purification. On standing for a day, the mother-liquor gradually deposited a crystalline solid which proved to be 8-ethoxyquinoline-5-sulphonic acid. It was crystallised from hot water in light brown, shining needles, m.p. 286-58° (decomp.), yield 3 g. It is readily soluble in aqueous sodium bicarbonate. (Found: N, 5.46. $C_{11}H_{11}O_4NS$ requires N, 5.53 per cent).

8-Ethoxyquinoline-5-sulphonamidophenyl-4'-arsonic Acid (I).—To a solution of *para*-arsanilic acid (12 g.) in a solution of sodium carbonate (6 g. in 150 c.c. of water) 8-ethoxyquinoline-5-sulphonyl chloride (14 g.) was gradually added with stirring. With effervescence a pasty mass was precipitated, which, on vigorous stirring with a glass rod, became granular solid powder. The solution at this stage was found very faintly alkaline. Anhydrous sodium carbonate (3 g.) and water (100 c.c.) were further added and the mixture was stirred with a glass rod for 3-4 hours, when an almost clear solution was obtained. Next day, the solution was filtered and the clear filtrate was just acidified with pure concentrated hydrochloric acid (just acid to litmus), when a heavy precipitate was obtained, which was filtered and washed with water. It is sparingly soluble in boiling water and was boiled with large quantity of water to remove any *para*-arsanilic acid. The residual solid was twice crystallised from alcohol as a colourless, crystalline powder, m.p. 242-44° (decomp.), yield 6 g. It is readily soluble in cold dilute hydrochloric acid and also in cold dilute aqueous sodium bicarbonate. (Found: N, 5.93; As, 17.01. $C_{17}H_{17}O_4N_2SAs$ requires N, 6.19; As, 16.57 per cent).

8-Ethoxyquinoline-5-sulphonamido-2'-hydroxyphenyl-5'-arsonic Acid (II).—The method of preparation was the same as in the case of the previous compound. 3-Amino-4-hydroxyphenylarsonic acid (12 g.), 8-ethoxyquinoline-5-sulphonyl chloride (crude, 14 g.) and anhydrous sodium carbonate (9 g.) were used. The reaction mixture was filtered and acidified with glacial acetic acid. On standing and scratching for some time, a precipitate was obtained which was filtered and washed with water. It is sparingly soluble in boiling water and was boiled 2-3 times with sufficient quantity of water and filtered. It is insoluble in hot alcohol and glacial acetic acid. For purification, it was dissolved in the requisite quantity of aqueous sodium carbonate and the solution, after being mixed with norit, was stirred for sometime. After filtration, the solution was acidified with acetic acid, when a colourless granular solid was obtained. It was filtered, washed with water and alcohol, and dried in the air. It was finally dried in *vacuo* at 120°, m.p. 215-17° (decomp.), yield 5.5 g. (Found: N, 5.72; As, 15.29. $C_{17}H_{17}O_7N_2SAs$ requires N, 5.98; As, 16.00 per cent). It is readily soluble in cold dilute hydrochloric acid and in cold aqueous sodium bicarbonate solution.

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